

ISSN 2181-9130

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9130

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 11 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 11

JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 11

ТОШКЕНТ-2024

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

№11 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9130-2024-11>

Бош муҳаррир:
Главный редактор:
Chief Editor:

Abdurasulova Qumriniso Raimqulovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:
Заместитель главного редактора:
Deputy Chief Editor:

Fayziev Shoxrud Farmonovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ | РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ | EDITORIAL BOARD

12.00.01 - ДАВЛАТ ВА ҲУҚУҚ НАЗАРИЯСИ ВА ТАРИХИ. ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАЪЛИМОТЛАР ТАРИХИ / ТЕОРИЯ ПРАВА И ГОСУДАРСТВА, ИСТОРИЯ ПРАВОВЫХ УЧЕНИЙ / THEORY OF LAW AND STATE, HISTORY OF LEGAL DOCTRINES

Boboyev Halimboy Boboyevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Ahmedshaeva Mavlyuda Axatovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Muxitdinova Firyuza Abdurashidovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Adilxodjayeva Surayyo Maxkamovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Sattorov Abdug'afvor
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Artur Gambaryan
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Armaniston)
Yosuke Shamoto
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Yaponiya)

12.00.02 - КОНСТИТУЦИОННИЙ ҲУҚУҚ, МАЪМУРИЙ ҲУҚУҚ, МОЛИЯ ВА БОЖХОНА ҲУҚУҚИ / КОНСТИТУЦИОННОЕ ПРАВО; АДМИНИСТРАТИВНОЕ ПРАВО; ФИНАНСОВОЕ ПРАВО / CONSTITUTIONAL LAW; ADMINISTRATIVE LAW; FINANCIAL RIGHT

Malikova Gulchexra
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Xusanov Ozod Tillabayevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Selimanova Svetlana Mixaylovna
yuridik fanlar doktori (O'zbekiston)

Xvan Leonid Borisovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Peshkova Xristina Vyacheslavovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (Rossiya)
Sung Un Lee
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Janubiy Koreya)

12.00.03 - ФУҚАРОЛИК ҲУҚУҚИ. ТАДБИРКОРЛИК ҲУҚУҚИ. ОИЛА ҲУҚУҚИ. ХАЛҚАРО ХУСУСИЙ ҲУҚУҚ / ГРАЖДАНСКОЕ ПРАВО; ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЕ ПРАВО; СЕМЕЙНОЕ ПРАВО; МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЕ ЧАСТНОЕ ПРАВО / CIVIL LAW; BUSINESS LAW; FAMILY LAW; PRIVATE INTERNATIONAL LAW

Oqyulov Omonboy
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Ro'zinazarov Shuhrat Nuraliyevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Ruziyev Rustam Jabborovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Borotov Mirodiljon Xomudjonovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Toshev Boboqul Norqobilovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Shomuxamedova Zamira Shoislamovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, (O'zbekiston)
Ahmad Issa Altweissi
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Iordaniya)

12.00.04 - ФУҚАРОЛИК ПРОЦЕССУАЛ ҲУҚУҚИ. ХЎЖАЛИК ПРОЦЕССУАЛ ҲУҚУҚИ. ҲАҚАМЛИК ЖАРАЁНИ ВА МЕДИАЦИЯ / ГРАЖДАНСКОЕ ПРОЦЕССУАЛЬНОЕ ПРАВО; ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЕ ПРОЦЕССУАЛЬНОЕ ПРАВО; АРБИТРАЖНЫЙ ПРОЦЕСС И МЕДИАЦИЯ / CIVIL PROCEDURE LAW; ECONOMIC PROCEDURAL LAW; ARBITRATION PROCESS AND MEDIATION

Esanova Zamira Normurodovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Mamasidiqov Muzaffar Musajonovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Jason A.
Kanton Federal sud markazi (AQSH)

12.00.05 - МЕҲНАТ ҲУҚУҚИ. ИЖТИМОИЙ ТАЪМИНОТ ҲУҚУҚИ / ТРУДОВОЕ ПРАВО; ПРАВО СОЦИАЛЬНОГО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ / THE LABOR LAW; SOCIAL SECURITY LAW

Usmanova Muborak Akmalxanovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Gasanov Mixail Yuriyevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Sattorova Gulnoza Djurakulovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Murodova Gulnora
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)
Denisov Gleb
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)

Fayziyev Shuxrat Xasanovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Usmonov Muhammadi Bahridinovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Xolmuminov Juma
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Jo'rayev Yuldash Achilovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Skripnikov Nikolay Kuzmich
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (O'zbekiston)

Po'latov Baxtiyor Xalilovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Salomov Baxrom Salomovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Salayev Nodirbek Saparbayevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Osmonaliev Qayrat
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Aleksey Kibalnik
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Kudryavtsev Vladislav Leonidovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Sergey Shoshin
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (Rossiya)
James B.
Eaglin Federal sud markazi (AQSH)

Rustambayev Mirzayusup Hakimovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Zufarov Rustam Axmedovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Kabulov Rustam
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Rajabova Mavjuda Abdullayevna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Taxirov Farxod
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Ismailov Isomiddin
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Hamidov Nurmuhammad Orif o'g'li
yuridik fanlar bo'yicha falsafa doktori (O'zbekiston)
Yuldoshev Rifat Raxmadjonovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Tojikiston)
Djansarayeva Rima Ernatovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Yelena Antonyan Aleksandrovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Matthew Light
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Kanada)

Inog'omjonova Zumratxon Fatxullayevna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Pulatov Yuriy Safiyevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
To'laganova Gulchehra Zaxitovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Muxiddinov Faxriddin Muxiddinovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Mirazov Davron Miragzamovich
yuridik fanlar doktori (O'zbekiston)
Rijakov Aleksandr Petrovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)

Stoyko Nikolay Genadyevich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Iskandarov Zayniddin
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Tojikiston)
Sergey Pen
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Aleksey Purs
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent (Belarus)
Jurgen Maurer
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Germaniya)
Kevin Curtin
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (AQSH)

Ismoilov Bahodir Islamovich
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Matkarimova Gulchehra Abdusamatovna
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)

Yuldasheva Govverjan
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (O'zbekiston)
Alexander Trunk
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor (Germaniya)

1. Бабаджанов Ҳиммат Хаджибаевич НОРМАТИВ – ҲУҚУҚИЙ ҲУЖЖАТЛАР ЛОЙИҲАЛАРИ ЭКСПЕРТИЗАСИ ТУШУНЧАСИНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	5
2. Baymurotov G‘ayrat Panjievich QONUNCHILIK HUJJATLARI LOYIHALARINI TAYYORLASH VA QABUL QILISHDA QONUNCHILIK TEXNIKASINING O‘RNI.....	13
3. Хуррамова Адолат Баҳодир кизи ҲУҚУҚ УСТУНЛИГИ (RULE OF LAW)" ДОКТРИНАСИНИНГ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯСИ ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	19
4. Abdullayev Jamshid Djamilovich FUQAROLIK HUQUQIY SHARTNOMALAR TIZIMIDA KOSMETOLOGIK TIBBIY XIZMAT KO‘RSATISH SHARTNOMALARIGA XOS NAZARIY VA AMALIY XUSUSIYATLARNI TAKOMILLASHTISH ASOSLARI.....	27
5. Донаев Абдукодир Ҳайдарович ҚУРИЛИШИ ТУГАЛЛАНМАГАН ОБЪЕКТ: МИЛЛИЙ ҚОНУНЧИЛИК ГЕНЕЗИСИ.....	35
6. Овулов Пўлатжон Илҳом ўғли ДАВЛАТ ИММУНИТЕТИ – ДАВЛАТ ФУҚАРОЛИК-ҲУҚУҚИЙ ЖАВОБГАРЛИГИНИНГ МУҲИМ ЭЛЕМЕНТИ СИФАТИДА.....	46
7. Raximova Dilorom Xaitbayevna BENEFITSIAR MULK VA UNING HUQUQIY TARTIBGA SOLISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	54
8. Israilov Dilshod Shavkatovich JAZONI YENGILLASHTIRUVCHI HOLATLAR TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING BELGILARI..	64
9. Зоирова Иродабегим Файзи кизи ВОЯГА ЕТМАГАН ЖАБРАНУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ҚОНУНИЙ МАНФААТЛАРИНИНГ ҲУҚУҚИЙ КАФОЛАТЛАРИНИ ТАКОМИЛЛАШТИРИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	72
10. Baratov Mirodiljon Khomudjonovich, Khakimov Ravshan Tulkunovich, Akramkhojayev Bori Tokhtahkodjayevich OUR RESPONSE TO EDWARD BALLISTEREY REGARDING THE PROBLEM AT THE WTO.....	79
11. Файзуллаева Нигорахон Равшановна АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ И КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ В СФЕРЕ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО КУЛЬТУРНОГО ПРАВА.....	87
12. Камиров Ойбек Хамиджонович КЛИМАТИЧЕСКАЯ МИГРАЦИЯ: ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНО-ПРАВОВЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ.....	94

12.00.10-МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЕ ПРАВО

Baratov Mirodiljon Khomudjonovich,

Head of Department of the Institute of State and Law
of Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Professor, Doctor of Sciences in Law

E-mail: mirodil707@mail.ru

Khakimov Ravshan Tulkunovich,

Leading researcher of the Institute of State and Law
of Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Doctor of Sciences, Associate professor,

E-mail: ngo_uzail@mail.ru

Akramkhojayev Bori Tokhtahkodjayevich,

Senior Scientific Researcher Institute of State and Law of the

Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Associate professor, Doctor of Philosophy in Law,

E-mail: 1370017a@gmail.com

**OUR RESPONSE TO EDWARD BALLISTEREY REGARDING THE PROBLEM AT THE
WTO**

For citation: Baratov Mirodiljon Khomudjonovich, Khakimov Ravshan Tulkunovich, Akramkhojayev Bori Tokhtahkodjayevich. OUR RESPONSE TO EDWARD BALLISTEREY REGARDING THE PROBLEM AT THE WTO. Journal of Law Research. 2024, 9 vol., issue 11, pp. 79-86

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14054338>

ANNOTATION

The authors of the article analyze the opinion of Edward J. Ballistreri regarding whether the United States is trying to undermine the WTO through a trade confrontation with China. The authors of the article express the wish that they support the opinion of Clayton Utter regarding the advantages of the United States in terms of marketing agricultural products around the world. And in terms of Uzbekistan's participation in the WTO, they express the wish for productive cooperation in this regard with the United States of America. At the same time, the authors cover in detail the course of Uzbekistan's promising accession to the World Trade Organization, including WTO assistance in organizing the World Trade Center in our country, as well as targeted negotiations between Uzbekistan and WTO members, and the US consent to Uzbekistan's participation in this trade organization. It is important that Uzbekistan may be able to use the status of a preferential participant in trade transactions with other WTO members for three years. This circumstance will undoubtedly contribute to the growth of our country's economy. It is not trade wars that should shake the world trading platforms, including the fragmentation of world trade into separate independent parts, but joint productive cooperation of all countries that are members of the World Trade Organization,

through which more than 98 percent of world trade is carried out. WTO membership will provide Uzbekistan with three levels of predictability. First, it will provide predictable conditions for access to the markets of trading partners. Second, WTO membership will protect Uzbekistan from unilateral trade measures imposed by other countries for geo-economic reasons. The WTO provides predictability with respect to any unilateral measures that may affect these conditions for geo-economic reasons. This protection is especially important in a world where global supply chains are being reshuffled and investors are increasingly seeking a stable environment. The third level of predictability occurs at the domestic level. By joining the WTO, Uzbekistan will be implementing reforms, especially at a time when the country wants to diversify its economy. This means meeting international standards, such as sanitary and phytosanitary regulations and technical barriers to trade, which are necessary to participate in global value chains. If Uzbekistan does not follow these standards, it will be very difficult for it to become part of this value chain.

Keywords: trade war, agricultural policy review, WTO, application of anti-dumping tariffs, Appellate Body, USA, Uzbekistan.

Baratov Mirodiljon Xomudjonovich,

Davlat va huquq instituti bo‘lim mudiri
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasi,
yuridik fanlar doktori, professor
E-mail: mirodil707@mail.ru

Hakimov Ravshan Tulkunovich,

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasi
Davlat va huquq instituti yetakchi ilmiy xodimi,
yuridik fanlar doktori, dotsent
E-mail: ngo_uzail@mail.ru

Akramxodjaye Bori Toxtaxodjaye Bori,

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasi
Davlat va huquq instituti katta ilmiy xodimi,
yuridik fanlar nomzodi, dotsent
E-mail: 1370017a@gmail.com

JSTDAGI MUAMMO BO‘YICHA EDVARD BALLISTERIGA JAVOBIMIZ

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqola mualliflari Edvard J. Ballisterining Qo‘shma Shtatlar Xitoy bilan savdo qarama-qarshiligi orqali JSTga putur yetkazmoqchimi yoki yo‘qmi, degan fikrini tahlil qiladi. Maqola mualliflari Kleyton Utterning butun dunyo bo‘ylab qishloq xo‘jaligi mahsulotlarini sotish bo‘yicha Qo‘shma Shtatlarning afzalliklari haqidagi fikrini qo‘llab-quvvatlashlarini istashadi. O‘zbekistonning JSTdagi ishtiroki borasida esa Amerika Qo‘shma Shtatlari bilan bu borada samarali hamkorlik qilish istagini bildirishmoqda. Shu bilan birga, mualliflar O‘zbekistonning Jahon savdo tashkilotiga kirishining istiqbolli borishi, jumladan, mamlakatimizda Jahon savdo markazini tashkil etishda JSTning yordami, shuningdek, O‘zbekiston va JST a‘zolari o‘rtasidagi maqsadli muzokaralar, AQSH roziligi bilan batafsil yoritilgan. O‘zbekistonning ushbu savdo tashkilotidagi ishtirokiga. O‘zbekiston JSTning boshqa a‘zolari bilan savdo operatsiyalarida imtiyozli ishtirokchi maqomidan uch yil davomida foydalanishi mumkinligi muhim. Bu holat mamlakatimiz iqtisodiyotining yuksalishiga xizmat qilishi shubhasiz. Dunyo savdo maydonlarini, jumladan, jahon savdosining alohida mustaqil qismlarga bo‘linib ketishini savdo urushlari emas, balki Jahon Savdo Tashkilotiga a‘zo bo‘lgan barcha mamlakatlarning birgalikdagi samarali hamkorligi, ular orqali jahon savdosining 98 foizdan ortig‘i larzaga keltirilishi kerak. amalga oshiriladi. JSTga a‘zolik O‘zbekistonga bashorat qilishning uch darajasini ta‘minlaydi. Birinchidan, u savdo hamkorlari bozorlariga kirish uchun bashorat qilinadigan shart-sharoitlarni ta‘minlaydi. Ikkinchidan, JSTga a‘zo bo‘lish O‘zbekistonni geoiqtisodiy sabablarga ko‘ra boshqa davlatlar tomonidan joriy qilingan bir tomonlama savdo choralaridan himoya qiladi.

JST geoiqtisodiy sabablarga ko'ra ushbu shartlarga ta'sir qilishi mumkin bo'lgan har qanday bir tomonlama choralar bo'yicha bashorat qilishni ta'minlaydi. Bu himoya, ayniqsa, global ta'minot zanjirlari inqirozga uchragan va investorlar tobora barqaror muhitga intilayotgan dunyoda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Prognozlashning uchinchi darajasi ichki darajada sodir bo'ladi. JSTga a'zo bo'lish orqali O'zbekiston, ayniqsa, mamlakat iqtisodiyotini diversifikatsiya qilishga intilayotgan bir paytda islohotlarni davom ettiradi. Bu global qiymat zanjirlarida ishtirok etish uchun zarur bo'lgan sanitariya va fitosanitariya qoidalari va savdodagi texnik to'siqlar kabi xalqaro standartlarga javob berishni anglatadi. Agar O'zbekiston ushbu standartlarga amal qilmasa, uning ushbu qiymat zanjiri segmentlaridan biriga aylanishi juda qiyin bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: savdo urushi, qishloq xo'jaligi siyosati sharhi, JST, antidemping tariflarini qo'llash, Apellyatsiya organi, AQSH, O'zbekiston.

Баратов Миродилжон Хомуджонович,

Заведующий отделом Института Государства и права
Академии наук Республики Узбекистан,
доктор юридических наук, профессор
E-mail: mirodil707@mail.ru

Хакимов Равшан Тулкунович,

Ведущий научный сотрудник Института государства и права
Академии наук Республики Узбекистан,
доктор юридических наук, доцент
E-mail: ngo_uzail@mail.ru

Акрамходжаев Бори Тохтаходжаевич,

Старший научный сотрудник Института государства и права
Академии наук Республики Узбекистан,
кандидат юридических наук, доцент
E-mail: 1370017a@gmail.com

НАШ ОТВЕТ ЭДВАРДУ БАЛЛИСТЕРИ ОТНОСИТЕЛЬНО ПРОБЛЕМЫ В ВТО

АННОТАЦИЯ

Авторы статьи анализируют мнение Эдварда Дж. Баллистери относительно того, пытаются ли США подорвать ВТО путем торгового противостояния с Китаем. Авторы статьи выражают пожелание о том, что они поддерживают мнение Клейтона Юттера относительно преимуществ США в плане сбыта сельскохозяйственной продукции по всему миру. А в плане участия Узбекистана в ВТО выражают пожелание о продуктивном сотрудничестве в этом плане с Соединенными Штатами Америки. При этом авторы подробно освещают ход многообещающего вступления Узбекистана во Всемирную торговую организацию, включая помощь ВТО в организации в нашей стране Центра мировой торговли, а также целенаправленные переговоры Узбекистана с членами ВТО, согласием США на участие Узбекистана в этой торговой организации. Важно, что Узбекистан может получить возможность в течение трех лет использовать статус льготного участника в торговых сделках с другими членами ВТО. Данное обстоятельство будет несомненно способствовать росту экономики нашей страны. Не торговые войны должны сотрясать мировые торговые площадки, включая фрагментацию мировой торговли на отдельные независимые части, а совместное продуктивное сотрудничество всех стран, входящих во Всемирную торговую организацию, посредством которой осуществляется более 98 процентов мировой торговли. Членство в ВТО обеспечит Узбекистану три уровня предсказуемости. Во-первых, это обеспечит предсказуемые условия для доступа на рынки торговых партнеров. Во-вторых, членство в ВТО защитит Узбекистан от односторонних торговых мер, введенных другими странами по геоэкономическим причинам. ВТО обеспечивает предсказуемость в отношении любых односторонних мер, которые могут повлиять на эти условия по геоэкономическим причинам.

Эта защита особенно важна в мире, где происходят перестановки в глобальных цепочках поставок, а инвесторы все чаще стремятся к стабильной среде. Третий уровень предсказуемости наступает на внутреннем уровне. Вступая в ВТО, Узбекистан будет проводить реформы особенно в то время, когда страна хочет диверсифицировать свою экономику. Это означает соответствие международным стандартам, таким как санитарные и фитосанитарные правила и технические барьеры в торговле, которые необходимы для участия в глобальных производственно-сбытовых цепочках. Если Узбекистан не будет следовать этим стандартам ему будет очень трудно стать одним из сегментов этой цепочки создания стоимости.

Ключевые слова: торговая война, обзор сельскохозяйственной политики, ВТО, применение антидемпинговых тарифов, Апелляционный орган, США, Узбекистан.

Edward J. Balistreri wrote the article "Is the US Trying to Undermine the WTO?" [1]. This article attracts with its transparency, so we, who are interested in Uzbekistan's participation in the WTO, decided to present this author's article in a special article with our comments on the future of the WTO.

A native of Eustis, Nebraska, Clayton Yeutter (1930-2017) was a tireless advocate for US agriculture. In his roles as the US Trade Representative and Secretary of Agriculture under the Ronald Reagan and George H.W. Bush administrations, Yeutter oversaw an unprecedented expansion of US agriculture into global markets and negotiated resolutions to bitter trade disputes, which, for example, resulted in the opening of Japanese markets to US beef and citrus. Yeutter envisioned a better way, however, where trade disputes could be resolved fairly under established international law. The World Trade Organization (WTO) emerged as a key component of the Uruguay Round of the renegotiation of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) [2]. Yeutter was instrumental in creating the WTO's dispute-settlement mission – a preeminent legacy. Starting in the mid-1990s, countries could bring trade disputes before the WTO as an impartial referee.

Chad P. Bown argues that «The dominant economic framework for the WTO [and the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) before it] involves governments of large countries using the institutional setting to coordinate policies to reduce the negative externalities they would otherwise impose on one another (Bagwell & Staiger 1999, 2002) [3]. Negotiations between governments have led to the reciprocal reduction of tariffs, allowing market access (trade volumes) to expand to levels closer to global efficiency and neutralizing what would have otherwise been negative terms-of-trade (price) impacts resulting from unilateral tariff reductions. Under this modeling approach, the WTO helps solve a prisoner's dilemma problem by coordinating policies to move from a noncooperative to a cooperative equilibrium among governments. This view of the WTO is sufficiently general that it can accommodate governments retaining considerable national sovereignty over their domestic policies, including the ability to respond to political pressures to use trade policy to redistribute between local interest groups. A growing body of empirical evidence, from a wide range of settings, broadly supports this interpretation of the WTO.

This research also documents how certain WTO principles help governments negotiate and reciprocally sustain open trade in practice. For example, the nondiscrimination across trading partners implied by the most-favored-nation (MFN) principle can help a world of more than two countries—where free riding and other concerns emerge—to initiate and sustain efficient bargains. Nondiscrimination between foreign and domestically produced goods (once the foreign good has paid the tariff) implied by the national treatment principle contributes to preventing a government from taking away the market access implied by an earlier tariff reduction commitment through subsequent resort to domestic tax or regulatory policy that may otherwise shift the costs of such policies abroad (see Horn 2006, Staiger & Sykes 2011).

The GATT/WTO also has guidelines that apply when governments seek to change policies in response to shocks. Governments should expect to compensate trading partners; as such, many legal scholars view the GATT/WTO as having liability rules, some of which can promote efficient breach,

which allow parties to break a contract when the costs of compliance (to the policy-changing country) exceed its benefits (to trading partners).

For example, a government can raise a tariff above its WTO legal commitment without having to explain why. Under GATT Article XXVIII, the tariff increase must be notified to trading partners and is then subject to negotiation, in which the default compensation rule is for adversely affected partners to be permitted a limited tariff retaliation to rebalance market access reciprocally if no other form of compensation can be agreed on.

Countries can also change their domestic policies. In some cases, the WTO provides guidelines on how to do so in ways that do not run afoul of its rules. However, even if a new policy violates WTO rules, the government needs to be prepared to bear the consequences (after being challenged through formal dispute settlement proceedings) that stem from tariff retaliation only, which is typically limited to restoring a reciprocal balance of market access. In both instances, the WTO does not prevent countries from making changes to their policies, and the recourse it permits is not punitive (for an early modeling approach and empirical evidence, see Bown 2002, 2004). The WTO reduces uncertainty by helping to define the limits to the costs for policy changes, broadly ensuring that the government has designed the policy for the right reasons—such as to address market failures or local externalities—and not to shift its costs onto trading partners through international price movements, thereby creating new international externalities» [4].

In 2023, the global economy faced a major test that had previously been avoided. Despite this, the post-pandemic global recovery managed to continue. In the US, consumers exceeded expectations and continued to spend, prompting many economists to abandon their negative scenarios and predict a rare soft landing. In China, a booming electric vehicle industry helped executives get closer to the growth target. In turn, India, which the authors call the new hope of the global economy, compensated for the problems of other countries.

The International Monetary Fund forecasts global economic growth at 2.9% in 2024, which is not much lower than last year. At the moment, two wars are “raging” on the world stage and about 40 national elections are planned, political events will shape the year. But critical points of economic stress can overturn the favorable prospects that the world economy has set itself on [5].

The WTO dispute-settlement mission is now under significant threat. The United States has chosen to block the appointment of new members to the WTO’s Appellate Body. Without an operating Appellate Body, the technical process for resolving disputes hits a dead end. The following quote is pulled from the WTO’s web page:

"Currently, the Appellate Body is unable to review appeals given its ongoing vacancies. The term of the last sitting Appellate Body member expired on 30 November 2020" [6].

The United States is actively engaged in strategically undermining WTO review because it knows that its actions cannot stand up to that review (Bown and Keynes 2020) [7]. By operating outside of the agreed rules, the United States is losing sight of Yeutter’s vision of an orderly trading system. The obvious risk for US agriculture is that all of the hard-fought market access, protected under WTO bindings, will be ignored by our trade partners and ultimately lost.

Trade disputes almost always arise when a country implements a so-called trade remedy against another country. Take the case of international dumping with anti-dumping duties (tariffs) as the trade remedy. WTO members agree not to sell goods in other countries’ markets at prices below the fair or normal price in their own market. It is considered unfair, for example, for a Canadian producer to sell lumber to a US distributor for \$1.00 per board foot when it sells the same product to Canadian distributors for \$1.50 per board foot. This is dumping, a type of WTO-inconsistent price discrimination that harms US producers. In the United States, we have laws that allow recourse in the form of anti-dumping duties, or tariffs, which brings the price of the Canadian export back up to the fair price of \$1.50 as it leaves Canada. Commitments made by the United States as a signatory to the GATT do not allow it to place arbitrary tariffs on Canadian lumber, but an anti-dumping duty is okay to the extent that the gross-of-tax price is roughly consistent with the fair price.

A trade dispute arises when the facts are in question. Canada may claim that the price differences, or some portion of the differences, charged by its firms are justified because of product

quality or contract-specific differences. More commonly, they may dispute the method used by the United States to measure price differences across many contracts and the method used to calculate the implied duty. In this regard, Canada may allege that the United States is the party violating WTO commitments by justifying a protectionist tariff under the guise of anti-dumping law. To the extent that Canada and the United States cannot resolve the dispute, the countries can bring the case before the WTO as a judge of the facts. If the United States implements the anti-dumping law in a consistent manner, Canada will have to either stop dumping or live with the US tariffs. If, however, Canada can show that the duties are unjustified or incorrectly calculated, the United States will need to modify its policy or face a set of retaliatory tariffs. Canada may then legally place tariffs on any US sourced products such that US exports reduce by a value equivalent to the Canadian export damage caused by the illegal US duties.

It is not surprising that the United States has adopted a hostile posture toward WTO dispute settlement in recent years. The United States seems to want to operate outside of the GATT rules, which it originally spearheaded, negotiated, and ratified. A couple of stinging losses for the United States at the WTO exemplify this – in 2019 the WTO ruled in case DS471 that the United States had imposed illegal anti-dumping duties damaging Chinese exports by \$3.579 billion per year on a set of 25 products (WTO 2019).

In January of this year, on a subset of those products, the WTO ruled in case DS437 that the United States had imposed illegal countervailing duties (another type of trade remedy) damaging Chinese exports by another \$645 million per year (WTO 2022). China originally brought these cases to the WTO in 2013, with the final decision going against the United States after years of stalling the inevitable. The decisions illustrate the United States' consistent violation of trade remedy procedures. The US violations in these cases precede, by many years, the recent trade war between the United States and China. Under WTO rules, the findings in DS437 and DS471 alone legitimize any set of Chinese tariffs on agricultural goods that reduce annual imports from the United States by over \$4.2 billion.

A simple example illustrates how the United States uses anti-dumping law to artificially inflate tariffs against its trade partners. A key component of case DS471 was the practice of zeroing by the United States Department of Commerce (USDOC) [8] in its calculation of the anti-dumping duties in question. Consider a set of transactions on a relevant product like Steel Cylinders imported from China. To simplify the example, let us assume that the fair price for Steel Cylinders as they leave the Chinese factory gate is \$5.00. Assume that the USDOC sees four transactions each of equal quantity – two transactions where Chinese firms sell to US buyers at a price of \$4.00 and two at a price of \$6.00. On average, are the Chinese firms dumping Steel Cylinders into the US market? The WTO would say no, the average price that the firms sells to US buyers is \$5.00, so there is no dumping and the appropriate anti-dumping duty is zero. The USDOC, along with the import-competing industry, have a different approach. They calculate the average price to be \$4.50, arguing that China is dumping by \$1.00 on two of the transactions and by zero (hence the label zeroing) on the other two transactions. The average of {1, 1, 0, 0} is \$0.50 so the USDOC calculates an anti-dumping tariff that effectively raises the price of all imports by \$0.50. WTO's Appellate Body consistently rejects this type of creative mathematics.

The United States inevitably, and predictably, loses cases before the WTO because it is unwilling to bring its policies and methods in line with its commitments under the GATT. Of course, now with no Appellate Body, there is no venue to hear the cases. Under WTO rules, the United States can appeal any case brought against it, but without an Appellate Body there is no one at the WTO to reject the established errors in the US methods. Could this be the US strategy to avoid losses at the WTO? If so, it is a short-sighted strategy because it fails to acknowledge the enormous benefits the United States gets out of having a rules-based trading system. At some fundamental level, trust in a set of rules and norms for international transactions facilitates trade. Clayton Yeutter saw these benefits in terms of marketing US agricultural goods across the globe. It has been a good run, but if we do not support and respect our institutions of law and order we cannot expect to depend on them when needed.

In our opinion, the United States needs to understand one simple truth: China wants to pursue a mutually beneficial trade policy with America without any trade wars and there is no need to fear China in trade matters, because China does not claim any privileges in trade relations, it is open to free trade with America and its sales market is very large. Is this worth causing a problem for the WTO?

In addition, look at the rapidly developing BRICS system, which in the future can easily compete with the WTO, and then the WTO's primacy in the world may really be shaken. Therefore, we fully support Clayton Utter's opinion regarding America's advantages in marketing agricultural products throughout the world.

And in terms of Uzbekistan's participation in the WTO, our country needs cooperation with the United States as the most experienced partner in trade matters, and strengthening trade and economic relations with this partner corresponds to the strategic interests of Uzbekistan in maintaining independence and further prosperity. Therefore, the United States should be no less interested in this issue than Uzbekistan. Moreover, during the meeting of WTO Director-General Ngozi Okonjo Iweala with the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an agreement was reached on the establishment of a Trade Policy Competence Center in Uzbekistan with the support of the WTO [9]. In addition, the Uzbekistan 2030 Strategy includes goal 93, which provides for the inclusion of Uzbekistan in the World Trade Organization as a full member of this organization [10], and Uzbekistan has held negotiations with 18 countries on accession to the World Trade Organization, of which 14 have already signed protocols on the completion of negotiations. This is an important step for the country's integration into global trade, which will be completed before the start of the 14th WTO Ministerial Conference in Cameroon in 2026 [11].

References/Иқтибослар/Сноски:

1. Edward J. Balistreri. "Is the US Trying to Undermine the WTO?"// <https://yeutter-institute.unl.edu/united-states-trying-undermine-wto>.
2. Final Act Embodying the Results of the Uruguay Round of Multilateral Trade Negotiations, Apr. 15, 1994, 1867 U.N.T.S. 14, 33 I.L.M. 1143 (1994) [hereinafter Final Act]; WTO Agreement: Marrakesh Agreement Establishing the World Trade Organization, Apr. 15, 1994, 1867 U.N.T.S. 154, 33 I.L.M. 1144 (1994) [hereinafter Marrakesh Agreement or WTO Agreement]; GATT 1994:General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade 1994, Apr. 15, 1994, Marrakesh Agreement Establishing the World Trade Organization, Annex 1A, 1867 U.N.T.S. 187, 33 I.L.M. 1153 (1994) [hereinafter GATT 1994].
3. The terms-of-trade theory of trade agreements Bagwell and Steiger (2002) is closely related to the trade conflict literature, since in their framework the external version of a trade agreement is a trade conflict in which countries choose politically optimal tariffs (which differ from standard Nash tariffs). The idea of politically optimal tariffs follows from the argument that governments do not necessarily maximize social welfare because they can extract contributions from interest groups (Grossman and Helpman, 1995)// <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2118226>
4. Chad P. Bown. Modern Industrial Policy and the World Trade Organization. Vol. 16:243-270 (Volume publication date August 2024) // <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-Economics-100223-041958>
5. <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2024-01-04/2024-global-economic-indicators-include-us-unemployment-china-real-estate?srnd=economics-v2>
6. <https://yeutter-institute.unl.edu/reviving-trade-justice-how-arbitration-saving-wto-dispute-resolution-now>
7. <https://cepr.org/publications/DPI4477> (application/pdf); Berthold Herrendorf & Richard Rogerson & Akos Valentinyi, 2022. "New Evidence on Sectoral Labor Productivity: Implications for Industrialization and Development," NBER Working Papers 29834, National Bureau of Economic Research, Inc.

8. <https://bookstore.gpo.gov/products/basic-guide-exporting-official-us-government-resource-small-and-medium-sized-businesses>
9. Президент Узбекистана подчеркнул важность скорейшего вступления страны в ВТО//<http://nhrc.uz/ru/news/the-president-of-uzbekistan-notes-the-importance-of-the-countrys-speedy-accession-to-the-wto> 5.06.2024.
10. Указ Президента Республики Узбекистан «О Стратегии Узбекистан-2030» от 11 сентября 2023 года №УП-158 // Национальная база данных законодательства, 12.09.2023 г., № 06/23/158/0694; 29.12.2023 г., № 06/23/214/0984 (Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Strategy of Uzbekistan-2030” dated September 11, 2023 No. UP-158 // National database of legislation, 09.12.2023, No. 23.06.158/0694; 12/29/2023, No. 23.06.214/0984).
11. Узбекистан хочет стать членом ВТО к 2026 году // <https://vzglyad.uz/ru/post/2024/05/30/wto> (Uzbekistan wants to become a member of the WTO by 2026 // <https://vzglyad.uz/ru/post/2024/05/30/wto>).

ISSN 2181-9130

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-9130

ҲУҚУҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 11 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ ПРАВОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 11

JOURNAL OF LAW RESEARCH

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 11

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000